

GERMPLASM IMPROVEMENT

Breeding methods

Performance of IRRI rice hybrids at Madurai, India

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We studied three IRRI-developed rice

hybrids and their parents during 1988 wet season (kharif). The semidwarf hybrids had medium duration, and long and broad boot leaves.

IR54752 A/IR46 R, with productivity of 26.65 kg/ha per d had the highest yield (see table).

Heterobeltiosis for yield (32% for IR54752 A/R54 R and 8% for IR54752 A/IR46 R) was not statistically significant.

The poor performance of IR54752 A/ARC11353 R was probably due to high incidence of leaf folder. □

Performance of hybrids and parents in Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India,^a 1988 wet season.

Hybrids, parents	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Boot leaf		Yield (t/ha)	Per day productivity (kg/ha)	Heterobeltiosis (%) for yield
					Length (cm)	Breadth (a)			
IR54752 A/IR46 R	128	103.3	6.8	25.74	40.9	1.38	3.4	26.65	8.32 ns
IR54752 A/IR54 R	131	99.1	10.4	23.90	23.8	1.56	3.2	24.73	32.08 ns
IR54752 A/ARC11353 R	128	110.9	6.2	23.70	27.7	1.58	1.2	9.53	-42.29*
IR54752 A	131	105.8	8.2	26.86	27.1	1.42	-	-	-
IR54752 B	135	99.0	9.0	26.04	27.0	1.44	2.6	19.55	-
IR46 R	130	82.5	12.4	19.10	22.6	1.44	3.2	24.23	-
IR54 R	131	78.9	8.4	19.26	24.5	1.44	2.4	18.72	-
ARC11353 R	141	90.4	9.0	18.86	23.7	1.52	2.1	14.99	-
LSD (0.05)	4.0	10.1	3.4	3.66	7.76	0.17	710		

^aThree replications; plot size: 9.6 m².

Effects of infection and imperfect closed-glume on germination of hybrid rice seed

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In commercial hybrid rice seed production, low germination and seedling survival sometimes cause problems. We have found that serious seed infection and unclosed-glumes make seed susceptible to adverse conditions and lead to low germination.

We examined 38 samples of 150,000 hybrid seeds 1985-87 at Lingling, Hunan; 41,698 nongerminated seeds had spots (73%) and unclosed glumes (19%). Spotted seeds were infected with pathogens, primarily *Alternaria*. Both infected and

unclosed-glume seeds had low specific gravity.

Infected seeds gave the lowest germination; unclosed-glume seeds had the lowest seedling survival. The germination × seedling survival rate was taken as a measure of Seed Effective Value (SEV). The SEV of all abnormal seeds was 50%, only 1/5 that of normal seeds. Germination of normal hybrid and conventional rice seeds did not differ. Infected and unclosed-glume seeds were 65.0 ± 13.8% in hybrids, 6.5 ± 1.7% in conventional rice seeds.

Germination and seedling survival of infected and unclosed-glume seeds decreased sharply under unfavorable rainy weather during seed production, high temperature and high moisture content during storage, and excessive seed soaking time (see table). □

Responses of hybrid rice seeds to stress. Lingling, Hunan, China, 1985-87.

Stress	Germination decline ^d (%)		
	Normal	Infected	Unclosed glume
Seed production during rainy weather ^b	14.2		25.6
Storage at high temperature ^c	33.6	90.5	71.9
Storage at high moisture content ^d	0.0	89.2	60.6
Excessive seed soaking time ^e	10.6	29.9	23.7

^aGermination decline (%) = $\frac{\text{germination under favorable conditions} - \text{germination under adverse conditions}}{\text{germination under favorable conditions}}$

^bWeiyou 6 seed production, autumn 1987. ^cComparison of av temp at 2 °C and 19.1 °C for 6-mo storage. ^dComparison between 8.8% and 14.0% moisture content for 6-mo storage. ^eComparison between soaking Weiyou 6 seed 0 d and 2 d after 15-mo storage.